

**E4.3: Final Prototype of Operational
Components and Toolkit for Smart
Contracts Enabled Negotiation
v1.0
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**DLT for 6G: Smart Marketplace
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

AIO	All In One
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business To Business
B2C	Business To Consumer
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRUD	Create-Read-Update-Delete
DID	DLT Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCM	LifeCycle Management
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
NS	Network Service
NST	Network Slice Type
OSM	Opensource Mano
RAN	Radio Access Network
SC	Smart Contract
SD	Smart Discovery
SDK	Software Development Kit
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtualized Network Function
VSC	Vertical Service Consumer
VSP	Vertical Service Provider
VSV	Vertical Service Vendor

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable *E4.3 Final Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation*, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). This deliverable updates E4.2 with operational extensions and final software toolkit for all components related to smart contracts enabled negotiation. It incorporates all the improvements, modifications and additional features that result from the defined workplan, and the feedback and experience gathered from the implementation and early integration. This deliverable consists of 1) final prototype implementation of platform components related to smart contracts enabled negotiation; and 2) updated document with modules installation and operation guidelines.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Document

Based on the initial prototype of deliverable 4.2 [1], this document provides the final version of two essential elements in the Smart Contract (SC) System, the SC Developer Toolkit and the SC State Composer (SCSC). For both components the final state of architecture, implementation, deployment and use is shown.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

Within the project, E4.3 is framed as the third and last delivery of tasks A4.1 and A4.2, both coming from the result of task A2.3.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The document is structured into multiple chapters that describe the development of the final SC System prototype, focusing on its two central components. Before the chapters, the lists of figures, tables and acronyms are included, along with an executive summary of the deliverable. The references used throughout the chapters are located at the end of the document.

- Chapter 1 (this chapter) focuses on tasks commitment and relationship with the work developed in the rest of the project.
 - It contains a new subsection, 1.4, which explains the improvements and updates applied to the components and data models in this deliverable.
- Chapters 2 and 3 completely cover the final version and functioning of the prototype of both the SC Developer Toolkit and the SC State Composer. All implementation details are included, as well as documented usage examples, to obtain a complete understanding of the components functioning.
- Chapter 4 includes the final data models used in both Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Consumer (B2C) scenarios.
- Chapter 5 includes an analytical conclusion to obtain a complete vision of the deliverable result.

1.4 Updates Overview

Updates to the E4.2 deliverable [1] have focused on finalizing the development to a final version of the system components. The SC System has not undergone any architectural modifications or changes to its technologies. Therefore, the most relevant updates include new functionality and tests that were not previously possible.

All updates contained in this document are listed in Table 1-1, distributed by the associated chapter.

Table 1-1 - Deliverable Updates

Chapter	Updates
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New command “decoder”: This command converts an attached encoded agreement of a model to its original file. This update affects subsections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.1: Scope and Functionalities • 2.1.2: Architecture • 2.2.2.1: Exposed Interfaces • 2.4: Functional Tests and Results - Attachment command works with HTML files: The ‘attachment’ command now allows to encode a HyperText Markup Language (HTML) file and convert it to the TM Forum attachment template. This update affects subsections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.4: Functional Tests and Results - Validate command includes a new check: The validate command now performs a check on the offer's asset type to see if the model contains all the expected fields. This update affects subsection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.2.2.1: Exposed Interfaces
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extra validations on endpoints: in the GET, POST and PUT methods, the existence/non-existence of DLT Identifiers (DIDs) is now verified. This update affects subsections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.1.2.2: Internal Operational Workflows - Integration tests on model exchanging: Tests on the sending and receiving of offers, orders and SC States with the APIs of other Marketplace systems. This update affects subsections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.5: Integration Tests and Results - New /render endpoint: A new endpoint, /render, has been implemented and integrated for the SC Dev Toolkit to request rendering of the Legal Prose Template. This update affects subsections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.2.2: Interfaces • 3.4: Functional Tests and Results

4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Update in data models: Some fields in the data models have been modified and new ones have been included to support the requirements of different assets. This update affects subsections:<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 4.1: B2B Scenario• 4.2: B2C Scenario• 4.3: Other Scenarios
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All new features and changes included in the table will be explained in detail in the corresponding sections.

In addition to these updates, the rest of the content in each section corresponds to that presented in E4.2 to provide a complete and comprehensive deliverable that reports on everything related to each prototype.

2 Smart Contract Developer Toolkit

2.1 Final Prototype Design

2.1.1 Scope and Functionalities

As described in [2] and [1] the SC Developer Toolkit is a component of the SC System in the form of a Command Line Interface (CLI) tool which is located outside the 6GENABLERS Marketplace platform. It mainly performs tasks related to filling in the input data models as All-In-One (AIO) JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) objects that the rest of the marketplace's components use. These models are 1) the offering AIO, 2) the order AIO, 3) the SC State AIO.

The way in which the developer creates each AIO model is based on an iteration process, depicted in Figure 2-1. From left to right, it begins by providing a simple description of what the AIO needs to reflect, then the developer will adapt the baseline AIO generated according to their needs, validating each new change. At last, the developer will move on to the SCSC component, described in chapter 3 to make use of the AIO in the Marketplace.

Figure 2-1 - Model creation process using SC Dev Toolkit

2.1.2 Architecture

The architecture of the component is based on two main parts, as shown in Figure 2-2, a command line interface and a Software Development Kit (SDK) library where the functionality is located. The developer interacts with the CLI by executing commands, which use the logic defined in the SDK to perform the requested functions.

Figure 2-2 - SC Dev Toolkit Architecture

2.1.2.1 CLI

The CLI is the released output of this component. It has a series of predefined commands, which were introduced in [2]. In the interest of focusing on the developer's needs and the simplicity of the process, some of these commands have been unified into one, while the functionality of others has been moved to the SCSC component. During the development of the prototype, it was decided to separate the functionality into four commands, summarized in Table 2-1. Each of them has a specific function, and their definition and use will be explained in the following subsections.

Table 2-1 - Command Suite

Command	Description	Example of use
Generate	Creates a baseline AIO document ready to be filled and customized.	A developer wants a Virtualized Network Function (VNF) offering template to start preparing the offer.
Attachment	Converts HTML files, PDF documents and compressed tar.gz files to an attachment valid TM Forum model ready to be included in an AIO.	A developer wants to include a PDF with the license model in the AIO template.
Validate	Validates an AIO document against a reference JSON schema of its type and semantics.	A developer wants to check if their customized AIO is valid to be uploaded to the Marketplace.

Decoder	Converts the attached content of the agreement of an offer or order AIO model to the original document type.	A developer has purchased a product and wants to check the Legal Prose fields of the order, which is rendered to PDF and encoded in the model itself.
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On the other hand, as indicated in Table 1-1 and explained in Table 2-1, a new command, i.e. the decoder command, has been defined which increases the functionality of the CLI for the user. This command allows the user to decode the attached agreement content from an offer or order AIO model, which has been downloaded through the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, from its published or purchased offers/orders section, or using the corresponding SCSC endpoint for this purpose. Figure 2-3 shows the usage flow of this command.

Figure 2-3 - Decoder command usage

2.1.2.2 SDK

Both, the SC Developer Toolkit and the SCSC components are built on top of an SDK where all the logic and functionality reside. This library is organized as described in the Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4 - SDK Internal Modules

- **Templates and Validation**

This module is dedicated to implementing the template generation and validation logic. It includes the templates that will be generated when the developer requests it and the schemas used in validation.

It is relevant to highlight that both syntactic and semantic validation takes place in the two components of the SC System in the Dev Toolkit when the user requests it and in the SCSC automatically when receiving an AIO document. Specifically, in the POST and PUT endpoints, to prevent any document from leaving the SCSC API without validation.

- **Digital Content**

This module includes the functionality that interacts with the user file system by creating attachment models for the chosen documents. The module is capable of processing documents, for example HTML documents, legal agreements in Portable Document Format (PDF) or compressed files in tar.gz format, such as the artifact of a VNF or Network Service (NS).

- **Render**

This module contains functions that specialize in rendering a PDF file using a template that is based on HTML files or in a unique file. This is the legal prose template. The functions obtain information from different AIO files and automatically generate a rendered PDF, included in the Product Order. Essentially, it analyses the legal prose template to inject the necessary values and return it for a final review before including it in the corresponding model.

- **Integrations**

This module is responsible for including integration points with the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and Smart Discovery (SD) services to be able to use the related functionality of these systems.

- **AIO LCM**

This module stores the logic related to the creation of the SC State, the functionality to process and translate messages received as events over the Data Bus to update the corresponding AIOs that are already stored in the DLT.

2.1.2.3 Internal Operational Workflows

Figure 2-5 - Offering Creation using SC Dev Toolkit

As can be seen in Figure 2-5 the user converts all documents, referring to price, licenses, and even the asset artifact itself into attachment models ready to be included in the resulting AIO.

Figure 2-6 - Order Creation using SC Dev Toolkit

Figure 2-6 shows the process of generating an AIO order. During the execution of the Validate command, if the AIO template is syntactically and semantically correct after the developer's modifications, the rendering process of the Legal Prose Template that is included in the associated offer begins.

There is no manual process involving the SC Dev Toolkit for creating the SC State AIO model since it is an automatic process which occurs when the instantiation of an order is requested.

On the other hand, in Figure 2-7 we can see the decoding workflow where a user wants to extract the Legal Prose PDF document that is encoded in base64 format within the agreement structure in an Order AIO model. The user must indicate the path of the AIO model as a parameter of the command. When the command is executed, a series of processes are started in the SDK to decode the desired content and generate the resulting PDF.

Figure 2-7 - Rendered Legal Prose decoding process using decoder command

2.2 Final Prototype Implementation

2.2.1 Technologies

The technologies used for the development of the SC Developer Toolkit have been chosen keeping in mind the functions that had to be performed and trying to ensure the minimal system requirement needed to use it. The CLI itself can be compiled on different operating systems, including Windows, any Linux distribution, MacOS, any BSD distribution, Illumos, Plan9 and Solaris. It is released as a standalone binary which does not have any system's library dependencies.

2.2.1.1 Go

Go [3], or Golang, is a programming language developed by Google, characterized by its simplicity and efficiency, and used to develop a wide variety of applications, from command line programs to distributed systems or high-scale applications. Some of the main features of Go are the following:

- Open-source project.
- Static typing.
- Compiled language, like C or C++.
- The binaries have the cross-compilation feature natively.
- It supports the object-oriented paradigm, but unlike other languages, it has no inheritance or other statements that indicate that it clearly supports this paradigm.
- It is clearly aimed at taking advantage of multiprocessor systems and network processing.

In the SC Dev Toolkit scenario, it has been used to develop both the main functionality of the SDK and the command suite.

It is also important to mention the Cobra library. This library focuses on creating modern command line interfaces in Go projects, and is used in large projects such as K8s, Hugo and GitHub CLI.

Cobra's high flexibility allows the creation of commands, nested commands, flags, command documentation and it is also POSIX-compliant. In the SC Dev Toolkit, Cobra has been the central part in the development of the CLI using the functionalities of the modules seen in 2.1.2.1.

2.2.1.2 JSON Schema

The data models implemented in the SC System, aligned with TM Forum [4] are written in JSON markup language. Due to this, the use of JSON schemas [5] in development has been necessary.

JSON Schema is a declarative language for validating the structure, constraints, and data types in JSON documents. It allows to define the expectations of the JSON file. This makes it simpler to exchange data between applications because the data follows a consistent pattern. Using these schemas ends up making JSON models more readable and improves data validation since applications can check the defined criteria.

Specifically, these schemas have been used to define the exact structure that the JSON models of the three existing AIO types (Offer, Order and SC State) should have. This functionality is precisely one of the parts that is behind the "validate" command seen in 2.1.2.1. Once the developer has completed their AIO model, that file is compared to its related schema.

2.2.1.3 Scaffold Go Library

Additionally, some tool or language was necessary that would allow the creation of an initial schema for the developer. In this way, the developer could have a first sketch of an AIO model that would be filled later. The option chosen was a scaffold template library that had synergy with Golang, specifically [6]. This library allows to define an initial structure of the AIO document based on some parameters provided by the developer. In this way, this first version of the AIO document adapts to those parameters and modifies parts of its code as necessary. This functionality is directly linked to the generate command, which was introduced in 2.1.2.1.

2.2.1.4 Chromedp Package

The package for Go, Chromedp [7], is a Chrome DevTools client that provides great functionality when performing tasks such as web scraping, unit testing or profiling web pages. This package has no third-party dependencies. In the render module of the SC Dev Toolkit, seen in 2.1.2.2, it has been used to process the HTML files that will include their information in the Legal Prose Template prior to rendering.

The process of generating AIO templates is complex, and it is necessary to have a global vision of all the related AIOs and how to reach the necessary fields to replace them in

the template. For this reason, the Offer AIOs will include a Legal Prose Template predefined by the SC System according to the type of asset being treated.

2.2.2 Interfaces

2.2.2.1 Exposed

The developer interacts with the SC Dev Toolkit through the CLI. The commands defined and exposed to the user are the access points to the functionality it offers, as seen in Figure 2-2.

- **Generate**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli generate -h
Generates an AIO template model for offer/order on the selected folder based on the developer preferences.

Flags:
  --type:
        B2B: The template is based on a B2B approach.
        B2C: The template is based on a B2C approach.

  --asset:
        VNF: The template follows the VNF asset structure.
        NS: The template follows the VNF asset structure.
        EDGE: The template follows the EDGE asset structure.
        CLOUD: The template follows the CLOUD asset structure.
        RAN: The template follows the RAN asset structure.
        SLICE: The template follows the SLICE asset structure.
        SPECTRUM: The template follows the SPECTRUM asset structure.

  --license:
        perpetual: The license model of the template is perpetual (in-full).
        opensource: The license model of the template is open-source (in-full).
        recurring: The license model of the template is recurring (rental).
        service: The license model of the template is as-a-service (rental).

  --pricing:
        flat: The pricing model of the template is flat.
        tiered: The pricing model of the template is tiered.
        subscription: The pricing model of the template follows a subscription model.
        payg: The pricing model of the template follows a PAYG (pay-as-you-grow) model.

Usage:
  scsccli generate [OFFER/ORDER] [PATH_TO_DIRECTORY] [flags]
```

Figure 2-8 - Generate command

The generate command shown in Figure 2-8 allows the developer, indicating the type of AIO document, to obtain a template of that document which contains the necessary placeholders and default values. The template is returned as a local JSON file. It is possible to pass some flags to this command to further customize the developer's preferences from the beginning, such as, for example, to indicate whether the template should be oriented to a VNF or NS among other assets. These possible arguments are explained to the developer using help or in the command extended description. The default values for these flags are the following:

- **Type:** B2B
- **Asset:** VNF
- **License:** Perpetual

- **Pricing:** Flat

- **Attachment**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli attachment -h
Generates an attachment model in a JSON file, ready to be included in an offer/order model, using an input
PDF, tar.gz or .html file

Usage:
  scsccli attachment [PATH_TO_PDF/PATH_TO_TARGZ/PATH_TO_HTML] [flags]

Flags:
  -h, --help  help for attachment
```

Figure 2-9 - Attachment command

Attachment command, shown in Figure 2-9, is used to fill attachments in AIO models. From the file path, the command returns a representation of the file in JSON, which is ready to be included in the offer or order template created by the developer.

Three variations of the attachment model are needed depending on the file. Some examples such as an agreement's PDF, monitoring scripts, the license model applied to an offer, and the pricing script for calculating the recurring cost of using the asset, can be directly encoded, and embedded in the document with their base64 representation [8].

Other files, such as the artifact of the asset (VNF/NS tar.gz file), are too heavy for this approach and, instead, the digital digest of the file is used to at least have a way of ensuring that said file is not changed after it is onboarded into the Marketplace.

Finally, there is the case of the Legal Prose Template, which is a document that must be encoded and attached to the Offer model but is in HTML format. The attachment command has received an extension with respect to [1] to support this conversion.

- **Validate**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli validate -h
This command validates a JSON model with an internal schema.json file, based on the type of JSON and the path to it.

Usage:
  scsccli validate [OFFER/ORDER/SCSTATE] [PATH_TO_MODEL.JSON]
```

Figure 2-10 - Validate command

Figure 2-10 command focuses on the validation of an AIO model by the developer. This validation compares the file selected by the developer with a predefined JSON schema of the specific AIO.

Additionally, this command includes an update from [1] Now, if an Offer AIO template is being validated, depending on what type of asset it contains, it is verified that all the characteristic fields of that type of asset exist in the model. This is done because the offer models of the different types of assets have very specific fields. Using the path to the file as input, the command returns an error if there is a syntax error, missing required field or incorrect value.

Furthermore, if the command is being executed on an Order AIO template, and is syntactically and semantically correct, a rendering process of the Legal Prose Template of the offer associated with this order is initiated. The SC Dev Toolkit requests this

rendering from the SCSC, and when it receives the rendered PDF, it includes it in the AIO Order model and returns the result to the developer.

Besides, the CLI implements marketplace-specific validations over the AIO to ensure that those files which other systems rely on to perform their functionality, are semantically correct with the rest of the AIO.

- **Decoder**

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli decoder -h
This command decodes the JSON B64 Encoded Agreement-Content into a new file (PDF, HTML) in this
folder using a JSON (OFFER/ORDER) as input

Usage:
scsccli decoder [PATH_TO_OFFER_JSON] [flags]
```

Figure 2-11 - Decoder command

The new command included in this deliverable, decoder, is responsible for extracting the encoded content of a model, specifically the agreement section, and decoding it to generate a file of the corresponding type in the current path. The normal use of this command is to obtain the rendered PDF of an order model in case a user wants to review it.

In any case, it has also been designed to be able to extract the template itself in HTML format from an offer, when it is not yet rendered. This can be useful, for example, in cases where a user has coded their legal prose template and included it in the offer, but later wants to modify some field before uploading the offer but has lost the original document, among others.

In summary, the decoder command always provides the option to retrieve encoded agreements from models.

2.2.2.2 Consumed

The SC Dev Toolkit only has one interaction with another component, the SCSC. This interaction occurs during the rendering process of the Legal Prose Template of an Offer, to include it in the validation of the Order AIO. The SC Dev Toolkit requests this rendering to an SCSC endpoint, which processes the request, generates the PDF, and returns it. This endpoint is of type internal and is defined as /render.

2.3 Final Prototype Deployment

2.3.1 Installation Procedure

Installing the SC Dev Toolkit is a simple procedure. To do this, simply download the binary, shown in Figure 2-12, from the Git repository of the project hosted at i2CAT's Gitlab, which can be accessed using the following link:

- <https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/atos/sc-state-composer>

By running the binary as Figure 2-13 shows it is possible to use all the functionality of the component. There is no library dependency on the user's computer and the generated Dev Toolkit binary.

Figure 2-12 - SC Dev Toolkit binary file

2.3.2 User Documentation

The user documentation for the SC Dev Toolkit can be found by running the help command, as shown in Figure 2-13. The developer can now see all the possible commands available to them and their explanation, as well as the arguments they can use, if any.

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scscli --help
CLI utility to assist on the creation of the AIO of a Smart Contract

Usage:
  scscli [command]

Available Commands:
  attachment  Generates an attachment model in a JSON file using an input file (.pdf, tar.gz or .html).
  decoder     Decodes the JSON B64 Encoded Agreement-Content from a model into a file of its original type in this folder.
  generate    Generates an AIO template model for an offer/order.
  help       Help about any command
  validate    Validates a JSON offer/order/scstate model.

Flags:
  -h, --help  help for scscli
```

Figure 2-13 - Help command

2.3.3 Integration Guidelines

The only necessary integration of the SC Dev Toolkit is with the SCSC, for the reasons explained in 2.2.2.2 about the rendering of the Legal Prose Template.

2.4 Functional Tests and Results

The results of using the SC Dev Toolkit have been successful and, as has been verified in 2.2.2.1 all commands are functional. Furthermore, this component is essential to show functional B2B and B2C scenarios since it is the first step in generating valid AIO documents. These documents are the final output of the SC Dev Toolkit and are detailed in Chapter 4. Additionally, functional and unit tests have been developed as part of the codebase of this component.

The existing functionality and flexibility will make this component a useful tool in preparing elements ready to be integrated into the decentralized 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

2.4.1 Deployment Status

Figure 2-14 shows the status of a SCSC node in one of the Kubernetes clusters. As it can be seen, it shows all the services, and pods deployed regarding the SCSC node.

```

danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/deployment$ kubectl get all -n scsc --kubeconfig kubeconfig_6genablers-dlt-3.yaml
NAME                                READY   STATUS    RESTARTS   AGE
pod/scsc-5cd7978646-zlf45          2/2     Running   0           19d

NAME                                TYPE          CLUSTER-IP   EXTERNAL-IP   PORT(S)          AGE
service/scsc-nodeport              NodePort     10.102.50.16 <none>        8080:30880/TCP  19d

NAME                                READY   UP-TO-DATE   AVAILABLE   AGE
deployment.apps/scsc               1/1     1             1           19d

NAME                                DESIRED   CURRENT   READY   AGE
replicaset.apps/scsc-5cd7978646    1         1         1       19d

```

Figure 2-14 - SCSC Deployment Status in a Kubernetes cluster

2.4.2 Commands Execution

Some examples of execution of the available commands are included to observe the results they offer. Figure 2-15 shows the correct execution of the generation of an offer template in the current directory. The generated offer file is called *offer-template.json*.

```

danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli generate OFFER . --asset=VNF
offer-template.json

```

Figure 2-15 - Using generate command

Next, Figure 2-16 shows the JSON file resulting from the previous execution of the generate command. Since flags were not included as arguments, the template was generated with the default values, such as the recurring pricing. The Legal Prose Template encoded is already included in the AIO template. Based on this template, and using other commands, the user can form the desired offer model.

```

"name": "Offering Template",
"description": "This JSON represents a Product Offering",
"version": "1.0",
"validFor": {
  "startDateTime": "1111-11-11T11:11:11.111Z",
  "endDateTime": "1111-11-11T11:11:11.111Z"
},
"category": [
  {
    "name": "VNF",
    "description": ""
  }
],
"place": [
  {
    "name": "",
    "geoLocationUrl": ""
  }
],
"agreement": [
  {
    "id": "",
    "description": "",
    "name": "",
    "agreementSpecification": {
      "name": "agreementSpec",
      "attachment": [
        {
          "id": "attachmentTemplate",
          "name": "TemplateB2B",
          "attachmentType": "file",
          "description": "Legal Prose Template for B2B purchases in a human legible format",
          "mimeType": "text/html",
          "content": "PCFET0NUwVBFiGh0Bww+CjxodG1sIGxhbm9ImVuij4KPgh1YwQ+CiAgICA8bWV0YSBjaGFyc2
+CiAgICA8bWV0YSBubW1lPSJ2aWV3cG9ydCIgY29udGVudD0id2lkdGg9ZGV2aWNlLXdpcHRoLm10aWFL
+QWdyZWVtZW50IGZvc1B0aGUuVHYy2hhc2Ugb2YgYSBwaXJ0dWFsIFByb2R1Y3Q8L3RpdGx1Pgo8L2h1YWQ
+CiAgICA8cD5bSW5zZXJ0IHRoZSB0ZXJ0cyBhbmQgY29uZG10aW9ucyBnb3Zlcm5pbmcgdGh.
PC9wPgo8L2JvZGh0CjVvaHRtbd4=",
          "size": {
            "amount": 7646,
            "units": "bytes"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  }
],
"serviceLevelAgreement": {
  "name": "basicSLA",
  "description": "Basic SLA for VNF/NS scenarios.",
  "version": "1.0",
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "name": "VSV",
      "role": "Seller"
    }
  ],
  "rule": [
    {
      "id": "availability",
      "metric": "availability",
      "operator": ".eq",
      "referenceValue": 99.9,
      "tolerance": 0.05,
      "unit": "%"
    }
  ]
},
"productOfferingPrice": [
  {
    "name": "",
    "description": "Purchase cost plus recurring price",
    "version": "1.0",
  }
]

```

```

    "price": {
      "unit": "EUR",
      "value": 0
    },
    "priceType": "subscription",
    "recurringChargePeriodType": "month",
    "recurringChargePeriodLength": 1,
    "prodSpecCharValueUse": [
      {
        "name": "recurring-payment-amount",
        "description": "This field defines the recurring amount to pay for using the asset.",
        "valueType": "integer",
        "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
          {
            "valueType": "integer",
            "value": "0"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  },
  "productSpecification": {
    "name": "",
    "description": "Product Specification offering media services",
    "resourceSpecification": [
      {
        "name": "Artifact",
        "description": "Tar.gz artifact containing an OSM-compliant descriptor",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "",
            "description": "Digest of the entire package per file",
            "mimeType": "text/txt",
            "content": "",
            "size": {
              "amount": 0,
              "units": ""
            }
          },
          {
            "id": "",
            "name": "License Model",
            "description": "This attachment references the license model applied",
            "mimeType": "application/pdf",
            "content": "",
            "size": {
              "amount": 0,
              "units": ""
            }
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "name": "naas",
        "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
          {
            "value": {
              "alias": "osm_vnfd_id",
              "value": ""
            }
          },
          {
            "value": {
              "alias": "naas_url",
              "value": "http://"
            }
          },
          {
            "value":

```

```

        {
          "alias": "naas_metrics_provider",
          "value": "http://"
        }
      ],
      {
        "value": {
          "alias": "osm_ip",
          "value": ""
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "vCPU Requirements",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "value": {
          "alias": "min-vCPU",
          "value": 0
        }
      },
      {
        "value": {
          "alias": "max-vCPU",
          "value": 0
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
        "value": {

```

```

          "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
          "value": 0
        }
      },
      {
        "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
        "value": {
          "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
          "value": 0
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "Storage Requirements",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
        "value": {
          "alias": "min-storage",
          "value": 0
        }
      },
      {
        "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
        "value": {
          "alias": "max-storage",
          "value": 0
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "function type",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "value": {

```

```

    "value": ""
  },
  ],
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSV"
    }
  ],
  "lifecycleStatus": "Unavailable"
},
"prodSpecCharValueUse": [
  {
    "name": "License Model",
    "description": "",
    "valueType": "string",
    "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "valueType": "string",
        "value": "recurring"
      }
    ]
  }
]
]
}

```

Figure 2-16 - Generated AIO Offer template

Something the developer could do now would be to encode his VNF artifact to include it in the template JSON AIO model. To do this, as shown in Figure 2-17, the attachment command is used.

```

danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli attachment openldap-knf-1.0.tar.gz
2024/05/27 13:27:39 The result of the command execution is in attachment resulting file.

```

Figure 2-17 - Using attachment command

The content of the resulting file, which gets a default name, specifically *attachment_from_file.json*, can be seen in Figure 2-18. Now, the user can include this attachment model in the offer template model.

```

danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ cat attachment_from_file.json
{
  "name": "openldap-knf-1.0.tar.gz",
  "attachmentType": "file",
  "description": "This struct represents the original .tar.gzfile converted to TMForum Attachment model",
  "mimeType": "text/txt",
  "content": "tCdIG4g1rZ257CpXD7MgvtKxZqxLMddAqmDCMfJh0f8=",
  "size": {
    "amount": 437,
    "units": "bytes"
  }
}
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$

```

Figure 2-18 - Resulting attachment model

The user must now modify the generated offer file with the specific values of his offer, including descriptions, pricing characteristics and desired attachments.

Next, and if the offer has already been filled in with the user's desired characteristics, it is time to validate the AIO. Figure 2-19 shows the execution of the validate command on this template.

```
danielruiz@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli validate OFFER offer-template.json
13:54:43.830 modelValidator.go:158 DEB 001 ▶ map[function type:true max-storage:true max-vCPU:true max-virtual-memory:true min-storage:tr
ue min-vCPU:true min-virtual-memory:true naas_url:true osm_vnfd_id:true]
13:54:43.830 modelValidator.go:161 INF 002 ▶ Success: The expected keys for this asset types were found! The validation will continue...
13:54:43.830 modelValidator.go:196 INF 003 ▶ The validation with the schema was successful. Your AIO JSON model is correct
```

Figure 2-19 - Using validate command

Both the validation of the key fields for the VNF asset type and the syntax verification with the JSON Schema have been successful, so the template model is valid to be uploaded to the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

Once the model is validated, the next step would be to upload it to the corresponding SCSC endpoint, which can be seen in 3.5.3. Subsequently, a stakeholder must place an Order for that Offer. This is shown in the 3.5.4. For the case of an NS that includes that VNF, the process is practically identical to the one just explained.

Finally, Figure 2-20 includes an example of the execution of the decoder command on a basic offer template. Since the Legal Prose is not rendered in an offer, what the command obtains is a resulting HTML file with the Legal Prose template.

```
@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli decoder offer-template.json
modelValidator.go:408 INF 001 ▶ Decoding was successful. Resulting file was generated.
13:07:56 Execution was successful. HTML file created.
```

Figure 2-20 - Using decoder command

Figure 2-21 shows a fragment of the beginning of the generated HTML file.

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <title>Agreement for the Purchase of a Virtual Product</title>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Agreement for the Purchase of a Virtual Product</h1>
  <p>This Agreement (the "Agreement") is made and entered into as of the [Date] by and between <strong>[Buyer Name]</strong>, with an address of <strong>[Buyer Address]</strong>.
  <p><strong>WHEREAS</strong>, the Seller is a vendor of virtual products on the <strong>[Marketplace Name]</strong> marketplace (the "Marketplace"); and</p>
  <p><strong>WHEREAS</strong>, the Buyer is a purchaser of virtual products on the Marketplace; and</p>
  <p><strong>WHEREAS</strong>, the Seller has offered for sale, and the Buyer desires to purchase, a virtual product (the "Product") described as follows:</p>
  <p><strong>[Product Description]</strong></p>
  <p><strong>NOW, THEREFORE</strong>, in consideration of the mutual covenants contained herein, the parties agree as follows:</p>
  <h2>1. Purchase and Sales</h2>
  <p>The Seller agrees to sell, and the Buyer agrees to purchase, the Product on the following terms and conditions:</p>
  <h3>1.1 Purchase Price</h3>
  <p>The purchase price for the Product (the "Purchase Price") shall be <strong>[Purchase Price]</strong> <strong>[Currency]</strong>. The Purchase Price shall be paid
  <h3>1.2 Payment</h3>
  <p>Payment of the Purchase Price shall be made through the Marketplace's secure payment system. The Buyer shall not be required to pay any additional fees or charges
```

Figure 2-21 - Legal Prose Template decoded from an Offer model

Figure 2-22 includes an example applying the decoder command on a final Order model.

```
@DESKTOP-SFGA6CF:~/xNF-SMART-CONTRACTS/scsc$ ./scsccli decoder orderAIO.json
modelValidator.go:408 INF 001 ▶ Decoding was successful. Resulting file was generated.
13:19:33 Execution was successful. PDF file created.
```

Figure 2-22 - Using decoder command with an Order Model

Finally, Figure 2-23 shows the first page of the PDF file resulting from the decoding of the rendered Legal Prose.

Agreement for the Purchase of a LDAP VNF Product

This Agreement (the "Agreement") is made and entered into as of the **04/05/2024** by and between **Daniel Ruiz**, with an address of C/ Constitución 1, 30007 Murcia, Spain, (the "Buyer"), and **Guillermo Gómez**, with an address of C/ Gran Vía 32, 46005 Valencia (the "Seller").

1. WHEREAS the Seller is a vendor of virtual products on the 6GENABLERS Marketplace (the "Marketplace"); and

2. WHEREAS the Buyer is a purchaser of virtual products on the Marketplace; and

3. WHEREAS the Seller has offered for sale, and the Buyer desires to purchase, a virtual product (the "Product") described as follows:

"OpenLDAP VNF with perpetual license and flat recurring price"

NOW, THEREFORE, in consideration of the mutual covenants contained herein, the parties agree as follows:

1. Purchase and Sale

The Seller agrees to sell, and the Buyer agrees to purchase, the Product on the following terms and conditions:

1.1 Purchase Price

The purchase price for the Product (the "Purchase Price") shall be **120 EUR**. The Purchase Price shall be paid by the Buyer to the Seller in full upon the execution of this Agreement.

1.2 Payment

Payment of the Purchase Price shall be made through the Marketplace's secure payment system. The Buyer shall not be required to pay any additional fees or charges in connection with the purchase of the Product.

1.3 Delivery

The Product shall be delivered to the Buyer electronically upon the execution of this Agreement. The Buyer shall be responsible for installing and configuring the Product on its own systems.

2. License

The Seller grants to the Buyer a non-exclusive, non-transferable license to use the Product for its internal business purposes. The Buyer shall not use the Product for any other purpose, including, but not limited to, commercial resale or sublicensing.

Figure 2-23 - Resulting PDF from decoding the order's rendered Legal Prose

2.5 Integration Tests and Results

The SC Dev Toolkit component has not needed integration tests because its only integration is the one it inherently has with the SCSC. For the correct functioning of the available commands, seen in 2.4, the existence of an integration between the two components is mandatory, which has existed naturally since the creation of the SC Dev Toolkit component.

Furthermore, one of the points where there is more integration between both components is with the rendering of Legal Prose, through the internal endpoint /render, which is explained in 3.4.

3 Smart Contract State Composer

3.1 Final Prototype Design

3.1.1 Scope and Functionalities

The SCSC is a central component of the SC System, deployed together with the rest of components forming the Marketplace, which allows interaction with the DLT. In addition, it represents the entry point for stakeholders who want to offer their resources and services or consult those provided by others. It also has communication with the Smart Discovery System, which allows a stakeholder to find available offers related to their interests based on an intent.

Finally, it reacts to alarms and events generated in other systems that organize and monitor the deployment of assets. In this way, the SCSC includes them in the corresponding DLT transaction and, if necessary, the availability of an already-integrated asset is modified so that other stakeholders are aware.

Other than the Application Program Interfaces (APIs) exposed to the stakeholders, the focus is threefold:

1. Creation of the SC State when an order is requested to be instantiated.
2. Rendering of the Legal Prose Template into a PDF document aggregating in a human-readable format, the legal binding of the transaction.
3. Perform the necessary LifeCycle Management (LCM) operations over the already validated offers and orders.

3.1.2 Architecture

The SCSC is based on a microservices architecture, a Rest API and a set of listeners to obtain events and alerts from the Data Bus. The Rest API focuses on three main things: Create-Read-Update-Delete (CRUD) operations for the required AIO (input data models) [9], CRUD operations for the SC State (output data model) [10], and interactions with the DLT system and the Smart Discovery system. Both the API and the set of listeners (Kafka consumer) are deployed in Kubernetes.

The SCSC has the characteristic of being a stateless element, that is, it does not retain information about the user's previous transactions. Each transaction is executed independently and without relying on the past stored anywhere else other than in the DLT. Due to this, the SCSC does not need to have an associated database, since it behaves as an element that processes requests and returns results in real time.

Figure 3-1 shows a diagram with the architecture of the component and its interaction both with a user through the Swagger UI and with other Marketplace components through its APIs or the Data Bus. In addition, the SDK block presented in 2.1.2 is shown as the SCSC also interacts with some of its modules.

Figure 3-1 - SCSC Architecture

3.1.2.1 Components

The two main components of the SCSC are the REST API microservice and the Kafka listeners, which is another API, but event driven.

- **Swagger API**

As presented in [11] the SCSC provides a REST API in the form of a web service that can be consumed directly from a browser. This service follows the OpenAPI v2.0 specification, and is organized into four sections to differentiate existing endpoints:

- Supply: Endpoints that allow offers to be uploaded to the Marketplace.
- Demand: Endpoints that allow the management of orders for existing offers in the Marketplace.
- Deployment: Endpoints that allow a way to consume previously ordered items from the Marketplace by requesting their instantiation.
- Internal: Endpoints that are necessary for the correct functioning of the system and interactions between the components of the SC System, for example, in the communication between the SC Dev Toolkit and the SCSC when rendering the Legal Prose Template.

This Rest API has been developed entirely in Go language and has been documented for a good understanding of its functionality using Swagger [12].

- **Listeners**

The SCSC has Kafka listeners to receive events and status updates through the Data Bus. These listeners can be seen in Figure 3-2 along with the rest of the Marketplace components that send alerts to the Data Bus.

Figure 3-2 - Kafka listeners

3.1.2.2 Operational Workflows

Figure 3-3 - Intent-based Offer Discovery Management

Figure 3-3 shows the interaction of a user who wants to discover new offers available in the Marketplace through an intent based on their preferences.

Figure 3-4 - AIO Document Reception Management

Figure 3-4 shows how a user sends an AIO document to the SCSC API that automatically validates its syntax and semantics before requesting its inclusion in the corresponding DLT API.

Depending on the type of AIO model, some actions or others will be performed. In the cases of Offer and SC State, there is communication with various endpoints of the DLT APIs to check metrics and resource availability. These processes will be explained in

greater depth in the sections on uploading offers and SC States through the Swagger UI, specifically the sections 3.5.3 and 3.5.5.

On the other hand, Figure 3-5 shows how the SCSC Kafka Listeners API receives an event and, as a result, a long process of updating that offer/order model and its associated SC State begins. Communication with the DLT APIs is performed by the SCSC API while event reception and updates are performed by the Kafka Listeners API.

Figure 3-5 - Event Management

Additionally, Figure 3-6 shows the rendering process of the Legal Prose Template through the internal render endpoint. This process starts when uploading an Order to the Marketplace through a POST to the corresponding endpoint of the SCSC API. The content of the Order is validated (as if the Validate command was run) for security, to avoid a case where the user has not validated the model for some reason. Once the content is considered valid, rendering begins.

Figure 3-6 - Rendering Process during POST Order process

This process must be differentiated from that seen in Figure 2-6. In that figure, the rendering of the Legal Proceeds is done by validating the Order model that the user has generated and customized with the validate command. In this case, the process starts because the user wants to upload the order to the Marketplace, so a security validation is done.

Finally, Figure 3-7 shows the instantiation process of an order previously acquired by a user. The associated orders, if any, are recovered and an SC State is generated for each one. This process includes the use of DLT APIs endpoints responsible for the creation, pre-deployment and deployment of SC States.

Figure 3-7 - Instantiation Request Management

3.2 Final Prototype Implementation

3.2.1 Technologies

Since the entire logic of the SC System is developed in the Go language, already presented in 2.2.1.1, the API and listener microservices for the data bus have also been developed in Go. The way in which these two microservices have been implemented will be explained below.

3.2.1.1 Swagger

APIs allow data and information to be shared between different elements in a system. One of the main problems they face is not having a common design standard or appropriate documentation. This slows down the way some elements interact since the connectivity between them must be taken more into account. One solution is to use an extended API framework, the best-known being Swagger [12]. With Swagger it is easy to create a set of rules and specifications to document the API, so anyone can understand how it works.

Swagger UI uses an existing JSON or YAML document and makes it interactive. With this, it creates a platform to organize the CRUD methods of the API and categorizes the operations. Each method is expandable, and it is possible to view the path parameters.

In any case, Swagger allows us to document our API, but not define its logic. To do this, it is necessary to implement some methods, in this case in Go, to define the actions of each API method.

3.2.1.2 Kafka Listeners

Also developed in Go, a Kafka listener consists of code that allows handling events in real time. The goal is to capture the time value of the event. In the offer and order scenario in a decentralized Marketplace, it is essential to listen to events that apply to already deployed services, since these events modify the behavior of the services. This microservice is implemented in the SCSC to handle the following events:

- Service Level Agreement (SLA) Violations
- Offering Violation Events
- Availability Notifications
- Deployment Statuses

3.2.2 Interfaces

3.2.2.1 Exposed

The exposed interfaces are divided into four sections: supply, demand, deployment and internal. Those interfaces can be seen in Figure 3-8. The purpose of these sections was presented in 3.1.2.1.

Smart Contract State Composer API ^{1.0}

[Base URL: 172.17.13.216:3080]
doc.json

Endpoint for stakeholder participating in the telco marketplace to onboard (offer and order), consult and deploy services

Terms of service
Guillermo Gomez, Daniel Ruiz - Website
Send email to Guillermo Gomez, Daniel Ruiz
Eviden (ATOS business) 2023

supply		^
GET	/productOffering	All productOfferings owned
POST	/productOffering	Create a productOffering
GET	/productOffering/{did}	One productOfferings owned
PUT	/productOffering/{did}	Update a productOffering
DELETE	/productOffering/{did}	Delete a productOffering
demand		^
GET	/discover/{intent}	Marketplace offers available
GET	/productOrder	All productOrders owned
POST	/productOrder	Create a productsOrder
GET	/productOrder/{did}	One productsOrder owned
PUT	/productOrder/{did}	Update a productsOrder
DELETE	/productOrder/{did}	Delete a productsOrder
deployment		^
GET	/smartContractState	All SCStates owned
POST	/smartContractState	Create a SCStates
GET	/smartContractState/{did}	One SCStates owned
internal		^
GET	/health	Health check of the service
GET	/render	Request the render of the Legal Prose Template
PUT	/smartContractState/{did}	Update a SCStates
DELETE	/smartContractState/{did}	Delete a SCStates

Figure 3-8 - SCSC API Exposed interfaces

3.2.2.2 Consumed

The interfaces that the SCSC consumes from other elements are the following:

- Data Bus:
 - o Events specified in 3.2.1.2.
- DLT APIs:
 - o SC State API
 - o Order API
 - o Offering API

- Smart Discovery:
 - o Intent-based Discovery API

The relationship between the messages received by the Data Bus and the events that the SCSC expects to generate is found in the Table 3-1. The messages and their nomenclature have been obtained from [13]. These events are included in the "Events" structure in the SC State AIO model.

Table 3-1 - Events and messages

Event	Associated received message	Sender	Purpose
SLA Violation Prediction	alert	Proactive SLA Monitoring	A potential SLA Violation has been predicted by the platform.
SLA Violation	alarm	Proactive SLA Monitoring	Indicates that any of the conditions or rules of the SLA have been breached.
Offering Violation	offering_violation	xNF Event Exposure module	Indicates that any of the conditions (e.g., pricing payment periods, storage or CPU values, etc) of the Offering have been breached.
Availability	availability_response	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Monitoring the availability of the resources of an offer.
Deployment Status	deployment_status	Broker Logic for Resource Controller	Indicates the status of an order deployment.

Figure 3-9 shows an example of the Offering Violation event format. This format was in development in E4.2 [1] . In this case, a violation has occurred with the payment period of the related offer of the order. Therefore, this event is raised and received by the data bus, and subsequently included in the SC State associated with this order.

This event is handled in the system during an internal process started by the xNF Event Exposure module, which is an external component that is responsible for detecting violations related to the conditions of an offer. This component is not planned in the project and is outside its scope, but in future deliverables execution tests will be included where the component will be mentioned for this violation event purpose.

```

{
  "events": [
    {
      "eventType": {
        "name": "OfferingViolation2",
        "timestamp": "1713430289",
        "description": "There was a violation of the payment period.",
        "violation": {
          "OfferingViolation": {
            "date": "1704897092",
            "id": "199762337890",
            "consequence": "alarm",
            "OfferingStatus": "Violated"
          },
          "orderId": "wwKYhmzXwTYpa",
          "status": "Resource ready",
          "SCStateId": "456"
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 3-9 - Offering Violation Event

3.3 Final Prototype Deployment

3.3.1 Installation Procedure

The deployment of this module is based on the use of Helm Charts. The first step to install the SCSC is to adapt the *values.yaml* file. This file, shown in Figure 3-10, contains information relevant to the deployment of the API such as the IP address and ports. It also indicates which image to use in the installation. On the other hand, there is also another section defined for the deployment of the Kafka listener that will get the events and messages seen in Table 3-1. This file is stored in the project repository hosted on i2cat's Gitlab, which can be accessed from the following link:

- <https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/atos/sc-state-composer>

```

image:
  api:
    tag: cicd
    image: gitlab.i2cat.net:5050/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/atos/sc-state-composer
    inPort: 8080
    outPort: 30880
    pullPolicy: Always
    sdUrl: 172.27.13.254:31111
    dltUrl: http://172.27.13.254:30547
  listener:
    tag: cicd
    image: gitlab.i2cat.net:5050/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/atos/sc-state-composer
    brokerUrl: 172.27.13.254:31090
    pullPolicy: Always

```

Figure 3-10 - Values.yaml file

The location of this file in the complete directory hierarchy is shown in Figure 3-11.

Figure 3-11 - values.yaml in repository folders

Now, the way to install SCSC is by running a command to install the helm chart, as shown in Figure 3-12.

```
helm install scsc --namespace scsc $PATH_TO_CHART
```

Figure 3-12 - Installing helm chart

`$PATH_TO_CHART` is equivalent to the root of the project, and then the command is completed with "cid/k8s-install/scsc-chart", as seen in Figure 3-11.

The result of the SCSC installation includes the following k8s elements:

- 1 pod: Two containers.
 - o Rest API
 - o Listeners
- 1 service: Nodeport to expose the Rest API.
- 1 namespace: scsc
- Configmaps and secrets for internal environment variables.

3.3.2 User Documentation

All the information and documentation necessary for a user to use the SCSC is stored in Swagger UI. The exact address depends on the installation but is based in the structure shown in Figure 3-13. The `outPort` value is taken from the `values.yaml` file shown in Figure 3-10.

```
cluster_ip:{values.image.api.outPort}/swagger/index.html
```

Figure 3-13 - Swagger.ui path

To interact with the SCSC, a user can only do so through the Swagger UI. In any case, there are some actions that can be easily executed, such as uploading an offer or order to the DLT APIs through the supply and demand endpoints available in the SCSC API.

A user can generate an offer or order template with the SC Dev Toolkit generate command and include that template in the request body of the endpoint in question. In this way, the user can quickly test the functioning of the system and see how models are uploaded to the Marketplace.

3.3.3 Integration Guidelines

As can be seen in Figure 3-14, a log of the Kafka listeners receiving messages through the Data Bus is shown. Listeners are constantly waiting to receive events. In this case, no events of any of the types handled are being received, but this demonstrates that a correct integration has been established with one of the essential parts of the system. Marketplace systems, such as the SCSC or DLT APIs, are integrated and communicating.

```
12:43:21.746 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0c9 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 1: [7]
12:43:22.743 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0ca ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:22.745 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0cb ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:22.745 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0cc ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:22.746 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0cd ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:23.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0ce ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:23.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0cf ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:23.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d0 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:23.745 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d1 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:24.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d2 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:24.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d3 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:24.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d4 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:24.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d5 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:25.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d6 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:25.743 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d7 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:25.743 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d8 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:25.744 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0d9 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:26.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0da ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:26.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0db ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:26.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0dc ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:26.743 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0dd ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:27.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0de ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:27.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0df ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:27.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e0 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:27.743 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e1 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:28.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e2 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:28.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e3 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:28.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e4 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:28.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e5 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:29.740 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e6 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
12:43:29.740 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e7 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of deployment_status at offset 3: [7]
12:43:29.741 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e8 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of availability_response at offset 3: [7]
12:43:29.742 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0e9 ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alert at offset 1: [7]
12:43:30.740 kafka_listener.go:17 INF 0ea ▶no messages received from kafka within the allocated time for partition 0 of alarm at offset 3: [7]
```

Figure 3-14 - Kafka listeners waiting for events

On the other hand, in 3.5.1 an example of integration directly from the SCSC API Swagger UI is shown, where a reception of the offers available from the SD is included. It is important to note that the integration with the SD System is the other major integration of the SCSC along with the DLT APIs.

Finally, the integration with DLT APIs is shown in 3.5.2, 3.5.3, 3.5.4 and 3.5.5, which includes examples of uploading offers, orders, SC State and obtaining previously uploaded models.

3.4 Functional Tests and Results

The deployment of the SCSC module is correct and functional, as previously presented in Figure 2-14.

The only functional test that can be performed in the SCSC, in addition to the internal tests to prove the correct development of the functionality, is about the render endpoint, which is shown in Figure 3-15.

This internal endpoint is called when a model is validated, either through the validate command by the user or automatically when uploading an order model to the marketplace through the API.

The endpoint triggers the rendering logic to transform the Legal Prose template into a rendered Legal Prose file in PDF format, and includes it encoded in the model where the template was. It is important to note that the call to this endpoint is only made when the previous validation steps have been completed, such as checking that the model being uploaded does not have a DID defined, and that the associated offer DID of the order already exists in the DLT.

Furthermore, is relevant to highlight that the endpoint does not accept parameters because everything occurs internally, and the endpoint is only called as a way of activating a series of internal processes that end with the rendering of the Legal Prose.

There are two cases in which this endpoint is called internally; when a user tries to POST an Order model or when he tries to validate it. In both cases, the SCSC already has the information about which AIO Order model it is, so the processes started with the /render endpoint have the necessary information to render the Legal Prose of that model.

Figure 3-15 - Internal render endpoint

Consequently, when accessing a validated order model, it is possible to observe that the Agreement structure where the Legal Prose Template is allocated shown in Figure 3-16 has changed, and now includes the encoded rendered file, as seen in Figure 3-17.

```

"agreement": [
  {
    "id": "legalProseTemplate",
    "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
    "name": "Legal Prose Template",
    "agreementSpecification": {
      "name": "agreementSpec",
      "attachment": [
        {
          "id": "attachmentTemplate",
          "name": "TemplateB2C",
          "attachmentType": "file",
          "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
          "mimeType": "text/html",
          "content": "+CgogICAgPGgyPjguIEdvdmVybmluZyBMlYXc8L2gyPgogICAgPHA+VGhpcyBBZ3JlZW1lbnQgc2hhbG0="
          "size": {
            "amount": 4374,
            "unit": "KB"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  }
]

```

Figure 3-16 - Legal Prose Template included in model before validation

```

"agreement": [
  {
    "id": "RenderedAgreement",
    "description": "Rendered Agreement for VNF Offering with perpetual license and flat recurring price",
    "name": "Rendered Agreement",
    "agreementSpecification": {
      "name": "agreementSpec",
      "attachment": [
        {
          "id": "attachmentPDF",
          "name": "Rendered Legal Prose PDF",
          "attachmentType": "file",
          "description": "Rendered Legal Prose in PDF format",
          "mimeType": "application/pdf",
          "content": "gAIG90aGVyIHB1cnBvc2UsIGluY2x1ZGluZyYnV0IG5vdCBsaw1pdGvKIHrvLCBjb21tZXJjaWFsIHJlc2FsZS90"
          "size": {
            "amount": 1163,
            "unit": "KB"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  }
]

```

Figure 3-17 - Encoded rendered Legal Prose included in model

3.5 Integration Tests and Results

3.5.1 Discovering Offers

The first of the integration tests consists of recovering all the offers available in the Marketplace belonging to other users. This allows a user, through an intent, to discover existing offers. The first type of intent is a "semi-natural" language, where the characteristics of the intent are specified by using the equal sign.

The selected semi-natural intent is: *"discover offers for offer_type=edge with memory=2, cpu=3, storage=500, location=Barcelona, price=300"*

Figure 3-18 shows the endpoint through the SCSC Swagger API, which communicates with the Smart Discovery System to retrieve offers.

Smart Contract State Composer API ^{1.0}

[Base URL: 172.27.13.254:30880]
doc.json

Entrypoint for stakeholder participating in the telco marketplace to onboard (offer and order), consult and deploy services

[Terms of service](#)

[Guillermo Gomez, Daniel Ruiz - Website](#)

[Send email to Guillermo Gomez, Daniel Ruiz](#)

Eviden (ATOS business) 2023

GET /discover/{intent} Marketplace offers available

Obtain relevant ProductOfferings AIO published (by others)

Parameters

Name	Description
intent * required string (path)	Intent-based request

discover offers for offer_type=edge with mem

Execute

Figure 3-18 - Discover offers endpoint using semi-natural language intent

```
curl -X 'GET' \  
'http://172.27.13.254:30880/discover/discover%20offers%20for%20offer_type%3D  
edge%20with%20memory%3D2%2C%20cpu%3D3%2C%20storage%3D500%2C%20location%3D  
Barcelona%2C%20price%3D300' \  
-H 'accept: application/json'
```

Figure 3-19 - Discover offers semi-natural final request

On the other hand, Figure 3-19 shows the final request that the endpoint sends to the SD System. The response with all the offers obtained is in Figure 3-20.

```

Response body
    "unit": "KB"
  }
}
],
"name": "agreementSpec"
},
"description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
"id": "LegalProseTemplate",
"name": "Legal Prose Template"
}
],
"category": [
  {
    "description": "Edge category",
    "name": "Edge"
  }
]
},
"cluster_id": 1,
"description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for an Edge resource",
"id": "2F5ZhuZrUX7KLa2x6ZJBRR",
"name": "Edge Offering with flat recurring price",
"place": [
  {
    "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
    "name": "Barcelona"
  }
]
],

```

Figure 3-20 - Discover offers semi-natural final response general information

Figure 3-21 shows the part of the response where the resources of the offer are located.

```

Response body
"productSpecification": {
  "name": "Edge spec",
  "description": "Edge Product Specification offering",
  "resourceSpecification": [
    {
      "name": "Edge resource",
      "description": "Specification of offered Edge resource",
      "attachment": [],
      "resourceSpecCharacteristic": [
        {
          "name": "i2slicer",
          "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
            {
              "value": {
                "alias": "slic3_type_id",
                "value": "65ca5b5aefe00f000a80d946"
              }
            },
            {
              "value": {
                "alias": "user_id",
                "value": "65c64afdfd050a000910e8d2"
              }
            },
            {
              "value": {
                "alias": "i2slicer_url",
                "value": "http://192.168.123.62:32135/"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 3-21 - Discover offers semi-natural final response resources part

Finally, Figure 3-22 shows the computing values established for the offer, specifically the CPU, memory and storage.

```

Response body
{
  "name": "cpu",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "value": 3
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "memory",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "value": 5632
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  "name": "storage",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
      "value": {
        "value": 140
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 3-22 - Discover offers semi-natural final response compute values

On the other hand, the second type of intent available is the natural one. In this case, the natural approach offers a more flexible way to write intents, like the way humans communicate. The chosen intent is *“I would like to retrieve offers for a vnf service with 2GB of memory, 500GB of storage, at least 3 cpus, located in Barcelona and with a price of maximum 300€”*. Figure 3-23 shows the endpoint using this type of intent.

GET
/discover/{intent} Marketplace offers available

Obtain relevant ProductOfferings AIO published (by others)

Parameters

Name	Description
intent * required string (path)	Intent-based request <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px; width: fit-content;"> I would like to retrieve offers for a vnf service </div>

Execute

Figure 3-23 - Discover offers endpoint using natural language intent

The final request sent to the SD Intent Based Discovery API is shown in Figure 3-24.

```
curl -X 'GET' \
'http://172.27.13.254:30880/discover/I%20would%20like%20to%20retrieve%20offers%20for%20
a%20vnf%20service%20with%202GB%20of%20memory%2C%20500GB%20of%20storage%2C%20at%20
least%203%20cpus%2C%20located%20in%20Barcelona%20and%20with%20a%20price%20of%20maximum%20
300%E2%82%AC' \
-H 'accept: application/json'
```

Figure 3-24 - Discover offers natural final request

The response with the offers obtained is shown in Figure 3-25. For simplicity, only one of them is shown, to confirm that it is a VNF type offer located in Barcelona.

```
Response body
{
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-10-14T13:50:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-11-30T13:50:26.456Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "Virtual Network Function",
      "description": "VNF category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "name": "TemplateB2B",

```

Figure 3-25 - Discover offers natural final response general information

Below, information on some relevant values of the offer such as the VNF descriptor ID in OSM or the metrics provider URL and port, is included in Figure 3-26.

```
Response body
{
  "name": "naas",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "osm_vnfd_id",
        "value": "bfd9bfd-9941-4d95-8cd6-32ff57d3e5d3"
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "naas_url",
        "value": "http://192.168.14.230:9191/"
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "naas_metrics_provider",
        "value": "http://192.168.14.10:9090/"
      }
    },
    {
      "value": {
        "alias": "osm_ip",
        "value": "192.168.14.144"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 3-26 - Discover offers natural final response resources part

3.5.2 Obtaining own Offers

Another of the basic actions of a developer is to recover all the offers that have been uploaded to the Marketplace. Figure 3-27 shows the endpoint and the request prepared to be sent to the DLT Offering API.

GET /productOffering All productOfferings owned

Obtain all ProductOfferings AIO published (your own)

Parameters

No parameters

Execute

Responses

Curl

```
curl -X 'GET' \
'http://172.27.13.254:30880/productOffering' \
-H 'accept: application/json'
```

Figure 3-27 - GET Product Offerings endpoint

The answer to this request can be found in Figure 3-28.

Response body

```
{
  "agreement": [
    {
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "attachment": [
          {
            "attachmentType": "file",
            "content": "gMyAwAAWjjjCCADp1sd44qwYwqPj4KZW5kb2JqCjQgMGBvYmOKPDwgl1Byb2NTZXQgwy...",
            "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "mimeType": "text/html",
            "name": "Template828",
            "size": {
              "amount": 1875,
              "unit": "KB"
            }
          }
        ],
        "name": "agreementSpec"
      },
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template"
    }
  ],
  "category": [
```

Response headers

```
content-type: text/plain; charset=utf-8
date: Tue, 28 May 2024 14:42:09 GMT
transfer-encoding: chunked
```

Figure 3-28 - GET Product Offerings endpoint response

3.5.3 Uploading a new Offer

When a developer has an AIO Offer Template ready and validated, they can upload it to the Marketplace through the endpoint shown in Figure 3-29. The complete AIO model has been included in the body of the request in the API.

POST /productOffering Create a productOffering

Create a ProductOffering AIO published (your own)

Parameters

Name	Description
body * required	Offer AIO model
object	
(body)	Edit Value Model

```

{
  "id": "",
  "name": "VNF Offering with perpetual license and flat recurring price",
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-05-28T13:50:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-05-30T13:50:26.496Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "Virtual Network Function",
      "description": "Virtualized Network Function Category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 3-29 - POST Product Offering endpoint

Figure 3-30 shows how the DLT Offering API has returned a DID associated with the offer. This DID is important, since in the next sections it will be used to place the order for this offer.

Response body

```
Gw7RuyyNTmwxtwbehpUASK
```

Response headers

```

content-length: 22
content-type: text/plain; charset=utf-8
date: Tue, 28 May 2024 15:15:44 GMT

```

Figure 3-30 - POST Product Offering endpoint response with received DID

For this offer to be uploaded successfully, the SCSC has had to consult internally three additional endpoints of the DLT Offering API during the execution of this POST, which are the following:

- GET /market/offer/metrics
- POST /market/offer/check
- POST /market/offer

First, the values of valid metrics to define the rules within the *serviceLevelAgreement* of the offer. This is done through a GET check to the */market/offer/metrics* endpoint. The SCSC checks the values of the rules established in the offer and compares them with the values obtained from the endpoint response. If they are valid values, it continues with the next check.

Secondly, the SCSC performs a POST to */market/offer/check* of the offer that the user wants to upload. This endpoint allows the user to know if the resources that the offer needs are available. If so, it continues with the last request.

Third and last, a POST is performed to the */market/offer* endpoint, and this is where the offer is finally published.

This entire process is transparent to the user, who only uses the endpoint in Figure 3-29. Therefore, it can be said that internally this SCSC API endpoint is subdivided into three processes that use three endpoints of the DLT Offering API.

3.5.4 Uploading a new Order

Additionally, the next logical step in the process would be to upload an Order model to the DLT Ordering API for the offer that was created earlier. The endpoint used and the request, which includes the Order model with the DID generated in the previous offer upload, are shown in Figure 3-31.

Figure 3-31 - POST Product Order endpoint

The response, with the new DID generated for this order upload, is shown in Figure 3-32.

Figure 3-32 - POST Product Order endpoint response with received DID

3.5.5 Uploading a new SC State

Finally, to create a new SC State using the DID generated in the previous section, the same procedure is repeated but with the endpoint shown in Figure 3-33.

Figure 3-33 - POST SC State endpoint

Figure 3-34 - POST SC State endpoint response with received DID

Figure 3-34 shows the response obtained from the call to the endpoint, where a DID is received because the SC State has been successfully created in the DLT Trading.

For this SC State model to be successfully uploaded, the SCSC had to query two additional endpoints of the DLT SC State API using the previously received DID, which are:

- POST /market/scstate/NkrbmjDihsprPABgSXdas/pre-deploy
- PUT /market/scstate/NkrbmjDihsprPABgSXdas

When a user uses the endpoint presented in Figure 3-33 to upload an SC State AIO model, the SC State is being created and stored in the Trading DLT, but its resources are not deployed. So internally, the SCSC executes the POST request to */market/scstate/{DID}/pre-deploy*. With this, the SCSC ensures that the resources needed when deploying this new SC State are available. If the result is satisfactory, the SCSC proceeds to make the second and last request, where the deployment of the SC State begins.

The last step is to execute the PUT request to the endpoint */market/scstate/{DID}*. This endpoint deploys the resources required for a previously created SC State in the DLT. If everything has worked correctly, the SC State is now deployed.

As with uploading an offer model, as seen in 3.5.3, this entire process is transparent to the user since he only uses the endpoint shown in Figure 3-33.

4 Final Data Models

This section focuses on explaining in detail the data model used in the system. With respect to the document [1], the data model has had changes based on the needs of development and integration with other Marketplace systems. The main reason for the changes, specifically in the offering models, is the adaptation to the needs of each type of asset. Considering that there are offers focused on different product types, such as Edge, Cloud or Network Services, and that each one has specific fields, the solution has been to adapt the general offer model for each situation. The project consortium has defined a final version of these models that will be explained in 4.3.

Next, a use case divided in two scenarios is presented, one B2B and the other B2C, which is maintained from [14], and that will be explained in 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. For simplicity, a VNF and a NS have been chosen directly from the OpenSource Mano (OSM) public repository to develop the AIO documents of the use case. This function and network service are focused on the deployment of a Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) service.

4.1 B2B Scenario

The B2B scenario replicates a situation in which a Vertical Service Vendor (VSV) wants to sell a specific simple service on the Marketplace. That service has been converted to a virtualized network function.

The service must be acquired through a fixed recurring amount that does not vary. Additionally, there are a series of documents which must be prepared before the offer is ready to be validated, such as the License Model or the Legal Prose Template. These documents are transformed into structures that can be included in the AIO using the SC Dev Toolkit, as seen in 2.1.2.1.

It is noteworthy to mention that AIOs contain an initially empty ID field when they are generated in the Dev Toolkit. This field is filled by the DLT with the DID when the AIO is received, as shown in 3.5.

The following sections will show each AIO document related to this scenario. These documents have a DID, simulating that they have already interacted with the DLT, to show their final form.

4.1.1 VNF Offering AIO

In Figure 4-1 a VNF Product Offering is presented. In this case, VSV has decided to customize its template with the following characteristics:

- **Place:** Barcelona.
- **License Model:** Perpetual. The rights for using the software are perpetual but are directly tied to compliance with the pricing schema.
- **Recurring Price:** The seller wants to generate benefits from the use of the VNF, so monthly he receives a fixed defined amount. The quantity is defined in the price structure, with an amount of 120 euros.
- **VNF Artifact:** The seller includes its own VNF artifact as an attachment in the offer.

- **vCPU, Memory and Storage Requirements:** The seller defines the number of vCPU cores, RAM and storage as requirements of the machine where the VNF is instantiated.
- **Function Type:** LDAP. The seller defines the scope of its VNF.

```
{
  "id": "SgoErzf25WSgjjzVwUvrGby",
  "name": "VNF Offering with perpetual license and flat recurring price",
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-05-28T13:50:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-10-1T13:50:21.496Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "Virtual Network Function",
      "description": "Virtualized Network Function Category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "name": "TemplateB2B",
            "attachmentType": "file",
            "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
            "mimeType": "text/html",
            "content": "gAofeOSANDNBVRCadCCAzA1sd44MyAwAqwYYwqPj4gL1Byb2NTZXQgWly=",
            "size": {
              "amount": 2134,
              "unit": "KB"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ]
},
```

```

"serviceLevelAgreement":{
  "name":"basicSLA",
  "description":"Basic SLA for VNF scenarios",
  "version":"1.0",
  "relatedParty":[
    {
      "name":"VSV",
      "role":"Seller"
    }
  ],
  "rule":[
    {
      "id":"availability",
      "metric":"availability",
      "operator":".eq",
      "referenceValue":99.9,
      "tolerance":0.05,
      "unit":"%"
    }
  ]
},
"productOfferingPrice":[
  {
    "name":"VNF Product Offering Price",
    "description":"Recurring pricing (flat, fixed amount)",
    "version":"1.0",
    "priceType":"Flat",
    "price":{
      "unit":"EUR",
      "value":120
    },
    "recurringChargePeriodLength":1,
    "recurringChargePeriodType":"month"
  }
],
"productSpecification":{
  "name":"VNF spec",
  "description":"Product Specification for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "resourceSpecification":[
    {
      "name":"VNF Artifact",
      "description":"Tar.gz artifact containing an OSM-compliant VNF descriptor",
      "attachment":[
        {
          "id":"openldap-knf-1.0.tar.gz",
          "name":"VNF Digest",
          "description":"Digest of the entire package per file",
          "attachmentType":"file",
          "mimeType":"text/txt",
          "content":"wAAWwAAjCCADp1sd44qwYYwqPj4KZW5kb2JqCjQgMGBvYmogMyAKPDwgL1Byb2NTZXQgWy...",
          "size":{
            "amount":1163,
            "units":"KB"
          }
        },
        {
          "id":"licenseModel",
          "name":"License Model",
          "description":"This attachment references the license model applied",
          "attachmentType":"file",
          "mimeType":"application/pdf",
          "content":"bb2JqCjQgMGBvYmoKPDwgL2Jqb2JqCjQgMGBvYmoKPDwgL2JqCjQgMGBvYmoKPDwgLgMyAwIFIGL01lyIDc5Ml0KPj",
          "size":{
            "amount":2264,
            "units":"KB"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
},

```

```

"resourceSpecCharacteristic":[
  {
    "name":"naas",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue":[
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"osm_vnfd_id",
          "value":"bfd9bfbfd-9941-4d95-8cd6-32ff57d3e5d3"
        }
      },
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"naas_url",
          "value":"http://192.168.14.230:9191/"
        }
      },
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"naas_metrics_provider",
          "value":"http://192.168.14.10:9090/"
        }
      },
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"osm_ip",
          "value":"192.168.14.144"
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name":"vCPU Requirements",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue":[
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"min-vCPU",
          "value":"15"
        }
      },
      {
        "value":{
          "alias":"max-vCPU",
          "value":"15"
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name":"Virtual Memory Requirements",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue":[
      {
        "unitOfMeasure":"MB",
        "value":{
          "alias":"min-virtual-memory",
          "value":"9728"
        }
      },
      {
        "unitOfMeasure":"MB",
        "value":{
          "alias":"max-virtual-memory",
          "value":"9728"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
],

```

```

    {
      "name": "Storage Requirements",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "min-storage",
            "value": "360"
          }
        },
        {
          "unitOfMeasure": "GB",
          "value": {
            "alias": "max-storage",
            "value": "360"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "function type",
      "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
        {
          "value": {
            "value": "LDAP"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ],
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "name": "VSV",
      "role": "Seller"
    }
  ]
},
"lifecycleStatus": "Available",
"productSpecCharacteristic": [
  {
    "name": "License Model",
    "description": "Bought once, used forever",
    "valueType": "string",
    "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "value": "Perpetual",
        "valueType": "string"
      }
    ]
  }
]
}
}
}
}

```

Figure 4-1 - VNF Product Offering AIO

4.1.2 VNF Order AIO

Figure 4-2 shows an AIO document of a product order of the VNF presented in 4.1.1. The Legal Prose already rendered to PDF is included as an attachment, and the relatedParty structure shows the two stakeholders involved in this transaction, the VSV that sold the offer of this VNF and the Vertical Service Provider (VSP) that has acted as its buyer through this order.

```
{
  "id": "MMKgoE33vgh78",
  "name": "VNF Order with rendered legal prose",
  "description": "This JSON represents a Product Order for OpenLDAP VNF",
  "version": "1.0",
  "orderDate": "2024-05-29T17:51.763Z",
  "completionDate": "2024-10-1T18:04.229Z",
  "state": "Available",
  "productOrderItem": [
    {
      "quantity": 1,
      "action": "add",
      "productOffering": {
        "id": "SgoErzf25WSgjzVwUvrGby"
      }
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "description": "Rendered Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "name": "Report PDF Document",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "name": "RenderedB2B",
            "description": "Legal Prose rendered with details of the offering and buyer",
            "attachmentType": "file",
            "mimeType": "application/pdf",
            "content": "PQgMCBb2JqCjQgMCAAujmjchanDCMADJqCj4KZvYmoKPDwgL1=",
            "size": {
              "amount": 1332,
              "units": "KB"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSV"
    },
    {
      "role": "Buyer",
      "name": "VSP"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 4-2 - VNF Product Order AIO

4.1.3 SC State AIO

Finally, Figure 4-3 shows a SC State model of the order presented in 4.1.2.

```

{
  "id": "WShhuyjcAYrppnQWly",
  "name": "SC State related to OpenLDAP Order",
  "description": "SC State generated on instantiation",
  "version": "1.0",
  "state": "completed",
  "order": {
    "id": "MMKgoE33vgh78",
    "description": "Product Order of the OpenLDAP VNF"
  },
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-06-01T10:11:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-10-01T10:14:33.456Z"
  },
  "place": [
    {
      "name": "Barcelona",
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "events": []
}

```

Figure 4-3 - VNF SC State AIO

4.2 B2C Scenario

This second scenario presents a situation in which a VSP wants to offer a form of access to a previously acquired VNF. The documents contain the DIDs of the other related AIOs.

4.2.1 NS Offering AIO

This document, although it belongs to a different scenario, is still a product offer, so the asset provider must also include a way to remunerate it as was the case with the VNF offer seen in 4.1.1. This, for example, is used to define a way of earning revenue that is more beneficial for the NS seller than the VNF seller.

In this case, the NS license model is also perpetual. The recurring payment, which occurs every three months, costs 500 euros. Finally, to that amount, the attached PLA adds different amounts as charges based on the use of the NS, such as time of use or resources consumed.

All legal documents related to the network service that the VSP wants to create must also be included, as this service is a completely new offer even if it depends on an element which already existed in the Marketplace such as the VNF.

In Figure 4-4 it is possible to find an example of this type of document.

```

{
  "id": "SppjuYHnxxxjby",
  "name": "NS Offering with perpetual license and recurring price based on usage",
  "description": "This JSON represents the Product Offering for OpenLDAP NS",
  "version": "1.0",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-05-29T17:52:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-10-1T13:44:21.496Z"
  },
  "category": [
    {
      "name": "Network Service",
      "description": "Network Service Category"
    }
  ],
  "place": [
    {
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona",
      "name": "Barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "id": "legalProseTemplate",
      "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "name": "Legal Prose Template",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [
          {
            "id": "attachmentTemplate",
            "name": "TemplateB2C",
            "attachmentType": "file",
            "description": "Baseline Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
            "mimeType": "text/html",
            "content": "VRCadCCAzA1sd44MyAwAqwYYwqgAofeOSANDNBPj4gL1Byb2NTZXQgWY=",
            "size": {
              "amount": 1632,
              "unit": "KB"
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "serviceLevelAgreement": {
    "name": "basicSLA",
    "description": "Basic SLA for NS scenarios",
    "version": "1.0",
    "relatedParty": [
      {
        "name": "VSP",
        "role": "Seller"
      }
    ],
    "rule": [
      {
        "id": "availability",
        "metric": "availability",
        "operator": ".eq",
        "referenceValue": 99.9,
        "tolerance": 0.05,
        "unit": "%"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```



```

        "value": "360"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "service type",
    "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "value": {
          "value": "LDAP"
        }
      }
    ]
  }
],
"relatedParty": [
  {
    "name": "VSP",
    "role": "Seller"
  }
]
},
"lifecycleStatus": "Available",
"productSpecCharacteristic": [
  {
    "name": "License Model",
    "description": "Bought once, used for ever",
    "valueType": "string",
    "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
      {
        "value": "Perpetual",
        "valueType": "string"
      }
    ]
  }
]
},
{
  "name": "Related Orders DIDs",
  "description": "References to previously placed Orders which need to be linked to this NS offering",
  "productSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "value": "MMKgoE33vgh78",
      "valueType": "string"
    }
  ]
}
]
}
}

```

Figure 4-4 - NS Product Offering AIO

4.2.2 NS Order AIO

Figure 4-5 shows an AIO model of a product order of a NS. In this case, the relatedParty structure shows two different actors than in the B2B scenario. The VSP now acts as the seller of the network service, and it is the Vertical Service Consumer (VSC) who through this order becomes the buyer.

```

{
  "id": "JHuibhYvCzzQtrh",
  "name": "NS Order with rendered legal prose",
  "description": "This JSON represents a Product Order for OpenLDAP NS",
  "version": "1.0",
  "orderDate": "2024-06-02T17:44.763Z",
  "completionDate": "2024-10-1T18:20.229Z",
  "state": "Available",
  "productOrderItem": [
    {
      "quantity": 1,
      "action": "add",
      "productOffering": {
        "id": "SppjuYHnxxxjby"
      }
    }
  ],
  "agreement": [
    {
      "description": "Rendered Legal Prose describing the offering in detail",
      "name": "Report PDF Document",
      "agreementSpecification": {
        "name": "agreementSpec",
        "attachment": [{
          "name": "RenderedB2C",
          "description": "Legal Prose rendered with details of the offering and buyer",
          "attachmentType": "file",
          "mimeType": "application/pdf",
          "content": "PQgMCBb2JqCjQgMCAAUjmjchanDCMADJqCj4KZvYmoKPDwgL1=",
          "size": {
            "amount": 1332,
            "units": "KB"
          }
        }]
      }
    }
  ],
  "relatedParty": [
    {
      "role": "Seller",
      "name": "VSP"
    },
    {
      "role": "Buyer",
      "name": "VSC"
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 4-5 - NS Product Order AIO

4.2.3 SC State AIO

Finally, Figure 4-6 shows the SC State resulting from the B2C scenario use case.

```

{
  "id": "aaJhhnMMkLlpnQWY",
  "name": "SC State related to OpenLDAP Order",
  "description": "SC State related to OpenLDAP Order",
  "version": "1.0",
  "state": "completed",
  "order": {
    "id": "JHuibhYvCzzQtrW",
    "description": "Product Order of the OpenLDAP NS"
  },
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2024-06-03T10:11:21.456Z",
    "endDateTime": "2024-10-01T18:22:33.456Z"
  },
  "place": [
    {
      "name": "Barcelona",
      "geoLocationUrl": "https://latitude.to/map/es/spain/cities/barcelona"
    }
  ],
  "action": "create",
  "events": []
}

```

Figure 4-6 - NS SC State AIO

4.3 Other Scenarios

The SC System will be able to handle offers focused on different types of assets. Specifically, these assets can reference a wide range of areas, which are VNF, NS, Edge, Cloud, Radio Access Network (RAN), Slice and Spectrum.

Since the areas to which an offer can adhere are very varied, it was necessary to have a robust data model that can adapt to all of them. For example, VNF, NS, Edge and Cloud offers have characteristics such as number of cores, amount of RAM or disk memory. On the other hand, a RAN service offer has operating bands, wireless technology, or frequencies.

TM Forum models have enough flexibility to adapt to these different scenarios, since there are fields in which any characteristic can be inserted. For example, "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue" is a structure where is possible to define a name, a type of the value, and the value. In this way an enormous number of specific characteristics can be described.

An example of this structure is presented in Figure 4-7, which shows the minimum and maximum virtual memory values that an NS supports.

```

{
  "name": "Virtual Memory Requirements",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "min-virtual-memory",
        "value": "9728"
      }
    },
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "MB",
      "value": {
        "alias": "max-virtual-memory",
        "value": "9728"
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 4-7 - resourceSpecCharacteristicValue for Virtual Memory NS requirements

```

{
  "name": "Maximum Downlink throughput per network slice",
  "resourceSpecCharacteristicValue": [
    {
      "unitOfMeasure": "kbps",
      "value": {
        "value": 100000
      }
    }
  ]
},

```

Figure 4-8 - resourceSpecCharacteristicValue for Maximum Downlink Throughput

On the other hand, Figure 4-8 shows another application of the framework. In this case, the maximum downlink throughput per network slice of a Slice type offering model is defined.

Table 4-1 shows all the specific fields for each type of asset.

Table 4-1 - Asset Specific Fields

Asset Type	Specific Fields
VNF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - vCPU (number of cores): min/max - Virtual Memory (MB): min/max - Storage (GB): min/max - Function Type

Network Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - vCPU (number of cores): min/max - Virtual Memory (MB): min/max - Storage (GB): min/max - Service Type
Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CPU (number of cores) - Memory (MB) - Storage (GB)
Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CPU (number of cores) - Memory (MB) - Storage (GB)
RAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RAN Type (Cell, Access Point) - Technology (4G, 5G, Wifi5, Wifi6) - Operation Band - Central DL Frequency - Central UL Frequency - Bandwidth (MHz) - Tx Power (W) - Duplex Mode
Slice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Area of service - Max downlink throughput per slice - Max uplink throughput per slice - Isolation Level - Data Network Access - Access Technology - Radio Spectrum
Spectrum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology (4G, 5G) - Operation Band - Frequency Downlink (Start/End) - Frequency Uplink (Start/End) - Duplex Mode

4.3.1 Integration Variables

To maintain the connection and integration with different entities of the Marketplace platform, the offer models have been adapted with respect to [1] to store specific variables with parameters and connection conditions.

These variables have been defined in a similar way to those seen in Figure 4-7 and Figure 4-8, using the resourceSpecCharacteristicValue structure. Table 4-2 shows what variables each offer has according to its scope along with a description of each one. RAN and Spectrum assets do not have specific variables.

Table 4-2 - Assets Integration Variables

Offer Type	Parameters and description
VNF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - osm_vnf_id: Identifier of VNF descriptor. - naas_url: URL (ip/port) of the NaaS instance managing offered resources. - naas_metrics_provider: URL (ip/port) of the monitoring server (based on Prometheus) exposing the metrics of the offered resources. - osm_ip: IP address of the OSM orchestrator.
Network Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - osm_nsd_id: Identifier of Network Service descriptor. - naas_url: URL (ip/port) of the NaaS instance managing offered resources. - naas_metrics_provider: URL (ip/port) of the monitoring server (based on Prometheus) exposing the metrics of the offered resources. - osm_ip: IP address of the OSM orchestrator.
Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - slic3_type_id: Identifier of the offered Network Slice Type (NST) from i2slicer slice manager. - user_id: Identifier of the tenant offering this slice resource. - i2slicer_url: URL (ip/port) of the i2slicer instance managing the offered resources. - i2slicer_metrics_provider: URL (ip/port) of the monitoring server (based on Prometheus) exposing the metrics of the offered resources.
Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - slic3_type_id: Identifier of the offered NST from i2slicer slice manager. - user_id: Identifier of the tenant offering this slice resource. - i2slicer_url: URL (ip/port) of the i2slicer instance managing the offered resources. - i2slicer_metrics_provider: URL (ip/port) of the monitoring server (based on Prometheus) exposing the metrics of the offered resources.
Slice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - slic3_type_id: Identifier of the offered NST from i2slicer slice manager. - user_id: Identifier of the tenant offering this slice resource. - i2slicer_url: URL (ip/port) of the i2slicer instance managing the offered resources. - i2slicer_metrics_provider: URL (ip/port) of the monitoring server (based on Prometheus) exposing the metrics of the offered resources.

4.3.2 AIO Schemas

The final AIOs in our use case are documents in which fields that contained direct IDs to other TM Forum models have been modified. Although the schemas selected to represent the structure of the AIOs are aligned with the official TM Forum version, small modifications have been made when necessary, such as the elimination of many of those

IDs since our documents are AIOs and the only IDs that are of interest to the document are the DIDs obtained by the DLT.

It is complex to find a single version of the TM Forum models and follow it in all cases, given that this organization has released numerous versions of them in the last decade. In some cases, to represent a specific characteristic, a schema from a previous version does accept it, and the later version modifies something that makes it not possible to include that characteristic.

For this reason, and given that all versions are valid, the most recent one has been used whenever possible. In the case of the offer AIO, this version [15] has been used. On the other hand, this version [16] has been used for the Order AIO. Importantly, since schemas have many dependent subschemas, a previous version of a schema has only been used when strictly necessary, so AIOs maintain a consistent and up-to-date structure.

The AIO model schemas are included in the repository along with all their dependencies, which can be found at the following link:

- <https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-dlt/atos/sc-state-composer/-/tree/main/scsc/pkg/models/aioschemas>

Finally, the JSON Schema of the SC State AIO model is the only AIO that is not built following any TM Forum specifications, as it is unique to the scope of the project but is inspired by their models to create the format of the fields and structures.

5 Conclusions

In this third version of the SC System, which means the final version of the prototype, the planned objectives have been achieved at the levels of functionality and integration. The behaviour of the SC System has worked as expected when testing the communication and exchange of data models with other entities, such as the Smart Discovery System or the DLT itself.

The SC Dev Toolkit constitutes the main tool for model management by developers, so any future development that adds value and improves the overall capabilities of the system will be considered.

In any case and given that the SC System is the gateway to the Marketplace, this system must always be able to incorporate any improvement related with the components usage or with the processing and validation of the data models.

6 References

- [1] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.2: First Prototype of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 31/01/2024
- [2] 6GENABLERS-DLT Project Consortium, Deliverable 4.1: Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0 – 30/09/2023.
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